

A New Synthesis of 9-Keto-trans-2-decenoic Acid

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5,5-Ethylenedioxyhexanol (II) was subjected to two carbons homologation utilizing four-step procedure to furnish alcohol (VI). Oxidation of (VI) with Collins' reagent produces aldehyde (VII) which is submitted to modified Wittig reaction with ethyl α -diethylphosphonoacetate to afford α,β -unsaturated ester (VIII). Ketoester (IX), obtained by the deketalization of (VIII), is hydrolysed to 9-keto-trans-2-decenoic acid (I).

A biologically active compound, known as "queen substance", is secreted by the queen honey bee (*Apis mellifera*). It inhibits ovary development in the worker bees and also queen-rearing within the colony.¹ The compound was isolated in crystalline state by two groups of workers²⁻⁵ and identified to be 9-keto-trans-2-decenoic acid (I).

Because of its biological importance, it has attracted the attention of organic chemists and consequently a number of syntheses for this compound have been reported⁶⁻¹⁰. In this communication, we now report a new simple synthesis based on the application of modified Wittig reaction of ethyl α -diethylphosphonoacetate on properly substituted aldehyde, for the creation of *trans* disubstituted α,β -unsaturated carbonyl system which is the characteristic feature of the structure. The sequence of reactions leading to the synthesis is outlined below :

5,5-Ethylenedioxyhexanol (II), prepared as described in lit¹¹, was smoothly transformed into its mesylate¹² by treating with methane sulphonyl chloride in the

presence of triethyl amine and CH_2Cl_2 as solvent at 10° . Mesylate (III), without further purification, was alkylated¹³ with sodium salt of diethyl-malonate to provide diester (IV) in 60% yield. The diester (IV) was subsequently decarboxylated by NaCl-DMSO ¹⁴ to furnish ethyl 7,7-ethylenedioxy-octanoate (V). The monoester (V) was safely reduced with LAH to the corresponding alcohol (VI).

Collins' oxidation¹⁵ of (VI) at room temp yielded aldehyde (VII) which was purified by chromatography over alumina followed by vacuum distillation. The aldehyde (VII) was submitted to modified Wittig reaction¹⁶ with ethyl α -diethylphosphonoacetate in the presence of NaH when the disubstituted *trans* α,β -unsaturated ester (VIII) was obtained in 75% yield. The ester (VIII) was deketalised by dil HCl in acetone¹⁷ at room temp to ketoester (IX) in 74% yield. Its structure was established through IR and NMR spectra.

Finally, the ketoester (IX) was hydrolysed with methanolic sodium hydroxide to obtain the title compound. The acid (I) was crystallised from methanol, m.p. $53^\circ-54^\circ$ (lit¹ m.p. $54^\circ-55^\circ$). Further confirmation of the synthetic ketoacid (I) was sought by comparing IR spectrum with that known in literature⁴.

Experimental

M. Pts. and B. pts. are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, as thin liquid film using NaCl optics. NMR spectrum was determined in CCl_4 using TMS as an internal standard at 60 MH_z .

1-Mesyloxy-5,5-ethylenedioxy hexane (III) : To a solution of the ketal-alcohol (II, 16 g) in methylene chloride containing triethylamine (15 g) at -10° , was added (11 g) methane sulphonyl chloride over a period of 20 min. The stirring was continued for additional 25 min. The reaction mixture was washed successively with ice-water, ice-cold HCl (10%), saturated Na_2CO_3 solution and finally with brine solution. The organic layer was dried (CaCl_2). Evaporation of the solvent gave the product (III, 16.4 g) which was used as such without further purification.

Ethyl 2-carbethoxy-7, 7-ethylenedioxy octanoate (iv): A solution of the above mesylate in dry benzene (40 ml) was added dropwise to a suspension of the sodium salt of diethyl malonate (prepared from 2.5 g of sodium and 16.5 g of diethyl malonate) in benzene (250 ml.) at room temp and the mixture was refluxed for 20 hr on water-bath. The contents after cooling were decomposed with water. It was extracted with benzene and the organic layer was washed with water and dried. The residue left after the removal of solvent was vacuum distilled to produce the diester (IV, 18g) in 60% yield, b. p. 170°/10mm. ν_{\max} 1730 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl). (Found : C, 60.04; H, 8.80. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 59.58; H, 8.67%).

Ethyl 7, 7-ethylenedioxyoctanoate (V) : A mixture of the diester (IV, 15 g), NaCl (5g), DMSO (100 ml) and water (3ml) was heated at 160° for 4 hr. The contents were cooled and then added to cold water and extracted with pet ether. The residue left after the removal of the solvent was vacuum distilled to produce the monoester (V, 7g) in 61% yield, b. p. 140°-45°/7mm; (Found : C, 62, 23; H, 9.45. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 62.58; H, 9.63%).

7,7-Ethylenedioxyoctanol (VI) : The ester (V, 11.5 g) was reduced with LAH (2.25 g) in ether (200 ml) as usual. Decomposition with sodium potassium tartrate and usual work up afforded the ketal-alcohol (VI, 7.5 g) in 80% yield, b. p. 130-35°/6mm. IR spectrum showed a peak at 3350 cm^{-1} (-OH) and no peak in the carbonyl region. (Found : C, 63.60; H, 10.35. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 63.79; H, 10.71%).

7,7-Ethylenedioxyoctanal (VII) : Chromium trioxide (15 g) was added to a stirred solution of pyridine (24 ml) in dry methylene chloride (100 ml). The yellow coloured complex thus formed was stirred for 15 min at room temp. To this a solution of the ketal-alcohol VI, 4.7 g) in dry methylene chloride (10 ml) was added dropwise. A tarry black precipitate separated immediately. After shaking the contents for 15 min, the reaction mixture was worked up as usual. Removal of the solvent and subsequent distillation gave the aldehyde (VII, 3 g) in 66.6% yield, b. p. 100°-105°/7mm; ν_{\max} 2710, 1710 cm^{-1} (-CHO). (Found : C, 64.78; H, 9.48. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 64.49; H, 9.74%).

Ethyl 9,9-ethylenedioxy-trans-2-decenoate (VIII) : To sodium hydride (0.76 g, 50% emulsion in mineral oil) in diglyme (25 ml) was added dropwise ethyl α -diethyl phosphonoacetate (3.6 g) with constant stirring keeping the temp at 20°. Into the resulting yellow solution was introduced the aldehyde (VII, 2.4 g) slowly below 10°. After stirring for another hour, the contents were heated at 50° for 3 hr and decomposed with cold water. The organic material was extracted with ether and dried. The solvent was expelled and the residue on distillation under vacuum provided α_1 β -unsaturated

ester (VIII 2.5 g) in 75% yield, b.p 130°-35°/8mm. IR spectrum exhibited a characteristic peak at 975 cm^{-1} (trans double bond). (Found : C, 65.80; H, 9.15. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 65.59; H, 9.44%).

Ethyl 9 - keto-trans - 2 - decenoate (IX) : The above ketal (VIII, 2.5 g) was dissolved in acetone (35 ml) and mixed with aqueous HCl (10 ml; 10%). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temp for 2hr. The solution was saturated with NaCl and the product was isolated with ether and dried. Removal of the solvent and distillation under vacuum afforded the corresponding ketone (IX, 1.56 g) in 73.6% yield, b.p. 120°-25°/10mm; ν_{\max} 1725, 1710 cm^{-1} (carbonyl). 60 MHz NMR spectrum showed signals at δ 1.17 (3H, t), 2.0 (2H, B), 2.1 (3H, s), 3.48 (2H, q), 5.91 (1H, d) and 7.1 (1H, m). (Found : C, 68.35; H, 9.15. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 67.89; H, 9.50%).

9-Keto-trans-2-decenoic acid (I) : A solution of the unsaturated ester (IX, 1.56 g), NaOH (0.5g) in water (1 ml) and methanol (4 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 hr on a water-bath. Methanol was removed under diminished pressure and the product was diluted by water. The unreacted material was removed by extracting with ether and the aqueous phase was neutralised with hydrochloric acid and extracted several times with ether. The extract was dried and the solvent stripped off to give crude acid (I, 1g). Recrystallization with methanol afforded pure acid (I), m.p 53°-54° (lit³, m.p. 54-55°). TIC showed single spot (Rf 0.54, benzene-ethyl acetate-ether 1 : 1 : 1) ν_{\max} 3400, 2955, 1750, 1695, 1645, 1435, 1415, 1375, 1315, 1290, 1245, 1220, 1170, 1170, 1100, 1055, 1025, 980, 945, 860 and 795 cm^{-1} . 2,4-DNP of (I) melted at 127°-28° (methanol). (Found : N, 15.29, $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$ requires N, 15.38%).

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